

Week 3 – practicing mapping mobility!

Written by: Adam Peacock (Institute for Sustainable Futures; Keele University)

Contact email: a.j.peacock@keele.ac.uk

Context: This practical has been written as a guide for the actual data analysis you will be completing as part of the project. You will be supplied with mock data this week so that you can learn the process. Once our data collectors have collected enough data, we will provide you with the research data. You should then re-use this guide to complete the analysis!

What we will be creating: We are going to be creating a heat map. Heat maps look at where data is most concentrated (heavily grouped together) and creates new data that reflects this. Our objective is to outline where people are using active travel the most. Let's open up a new project on QGIS and get started!

Part 1: Setting the Coordinate Reference System

As you'll remember from the first practical, you need to tell QGIS where in the world to find the data. We need to set the **Coordinate Reference System – CRS**.

A CRS is how QGIS can tell where we are in the world. It's like putting your home address into Google Maps so it knows where you are!

A CRS make sure all our data stays in the right place.

1. Go to

project < properties.

Figure 1. Where the properties menu is in QGIS.

2. The menu below in figure 2 should pop up. On the left, select CRS (first hashed box on figure 2).
3. Where it says filter (second hashed box on figure 2), type in EPSG:4326.
4. You should have WGS84 appear. Click it.
5. Click apply (down the bottom), then click ok (next to apply).

Figure 2. How to find WGS84

You'll notice this is a different projection to the one we used in week 1. This CRS gives us a much better result for linking our data together. This shows how important it is to think about the CRS that you use!

Part 2: Adding Google maps

We firstly need to add a map so we can contextualise the data. We're going to add a google maps layer, as we did in week 1.

- Head to the browser window on the left side of your screen.

Remember: If you do not see the browser window, you may need to active it. You can find it in: View < Panels < tick browser. (Figure 3)

7. On the browser window, **right click** on XYZ tiles.

Figure 4: Where the XYZ tiles is.

8. Choose New Connection.
9. In the XYZ connection window, where it says Name, enter 'Google maps'.
10. Where it says URL, copy and paste the following:

<https://mt1.google.com/vt/lyrs=r&x={x}&y={y}&z={z}>

What you are doing here is telling QGIS **where** it can find Google Maps **online**. This is really useful because it can tap into online databases as well as those on your computer!

11. Set the Max. Zoom level to 19. This tells QGIS how far out to zoom the map. I have selected this to show you how the world is quite literally at your disposal!
12. Click ok.

This should look like **figure 5** below if you get stuck!

Figure 5: How the XYZ connection should look before clicking OK. Google Maps

Don't panic if nothing has popped up! You should see Google maps under your XYZ Tiles area (figure 6 below)

Figure 6: Google maps under XYZ tiles.

13. Left click on Google maps (as above) and drag it right to the map area.

If all has gone as planned, you should see a map of the world appear!

14. Use the Pan and Zoom tools to find Rugeley (as you did previously in week 1 – Figure 7)

Figure 7: Where Rugeley is located in the UK

15. Zoom to the Brereton area!

Part 3: Adding the mobility data

For the purpose of this practical, I have created some mobility data for you to practice with. I've created two data sets – one is based on walking patterns, the other on cycling patterns. Lets start by adding both data sets to QGIS.

16. Go to layer < add layer < add vector layer (figure 8)

Figure 8: where to find 'add vector layer'

17. In the add vector layer window (figure 9), click "..."
18. Hold CTRL down on your keyboard and click on the 'Walking.shp', 'cycling1.shp' and 'cycling2.shp' files.
19. Click add.

Figure 9: the add vector data window.

You should have the following data added! Don't worry if the colors are different!

Figure 10: The mobility data

You'll notice there are two different cycling route datasets. We need these to be merged together, or the final result will not be representative. Think about it like this, at the moment, our cycling data looks like figure 11 below. They are two different layers on top of each other. In order to get accurate results, we need them to look like figure 12 - to be on the same level.

Figure 11: A representation of our different data layers stacked on top of each other.

Figure 12: A representation of our different data layers stacked on top of each other with both layers now merged on to the same level.

The real dataset will have hundreds of data sets, but Josh will merge these for you. Nonetheless, it is useful for you to learn how to do this!

20. Go to **Vector < Data Management Tools < Merge Vector Layers**

Figure 13. Where to find Merge vector layers

21. Select the cycling 1 and cycling 2 layers and click OK (figure 14).
22. Set the Destination CRS to **Project CRS: EPSG 3857 - WGS 84 / Pseudo Mercator**
23. In the 'Merged' box, click the "..." button and navigate to the folder where your data is saved. Type the name 'merge' and then click ok.
24. Click Run on the merge data window.

Figure 14: The merge vector data window

27. Right click on the merged layer in your layers panel.
28. Click properties.
29. On the left side of the screen, look for this symbol and click it. This opens the 'symbology' window.
30. Change the top box to **Heatmap**.
31. On the colour ramp row, click the small arrow on the right hand side. Change the color ramp to 'reds'.
32. Set the radius to 5.0
33. Down the bottom you will see the 'layer rendering' tab. Click it.
34. Set the opacity to approximately 40%
35. Click apply, then ok.

Figure 16: The symbology tab and where settings are located.

If all has gone as planned, your data should now look like figure 17! What QGIS has done is look at where there are the most dots and make these areas darker than the other areas! Now we can see where people have been cycling the most.

Figure 17: The heatmap output.

36. Repeat steps 27 to 35 for the walking data, but instead of setting the colour ramp to red, set it to blue!

Your final output should look like figure 18!

Figure 18: Heatmaps showing the most used routes for cycling (red) and walking (blue) in Brereton